

Interviewees' Smartphone Usage

Table 1: To better understand our interviewees' smartphone usage, we describe the apps and features they reported having installed or using on their smartphone.

	Popularity Among Interviewees	Category	Examples
Installed/used on more than 50% of phones.		Browser	Chrome, Safari, Firefox
		Cloud Storage and Documents	Dropbox, Google Drive, OneDrive, NextCloud
		Messengers	WhatsApp, WeChat, Telegram, Facebook Messenger
		Music	Spotify, YouTube Music, Apple Music
		Social Media	Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, X, Threads, TikTok, SnapChat
		Personal Productivity	Email, Calendar, Contacts, Documents
		Entertainment	Netflix, Amazon Prime, Disney+, YouTube
		Photos and Videos	Photos stored on your phone, iCloud Photos, Google Photos
		Wallet	Credit Cards, Membership Cards, Boardingpasses and Tickets
		Navigation	Google Maps, Waze Navigation
		Business Communication	Microsoft Teams, Slack, Zoom Workplace
		Finance	PayPal, Venmo, Online Banking, Trading
		Food and Drinks	McDonald's, Uber Eats, Delivery Hero
		Weather	AccuWeather, The Weather Channel
		Business Productivity	Email, Calendar, Contacts, Documents
		Shopping	Amazon, IKEA, Temu, Walmart, Best Buy, Wish
		Health	Period tracker, Sleep tracker, Heart monitor, Doctolib
	Installed/used on less than 50% of phones.		Education
		Ride Sharing	Uber, Lyft, Taxi
		Security Tools	Password Manager, 2FA codes, Vault Apps
		Personal Assistance	Alexa, Siri, Google Assistant, ChatGPT
		Location Sharing	Temporarily/permanently, Find My, Within Messengers
		Travel	Booking.com, American Airlines, Airbnb, Amtrak
		Utilities	Shipment Tracking, Document Scanner, Calculator
		VPN	NordVPN, Proton VPN, CyberGhost, CISCO, Wireguard, IPSEC
		Games	Subway Surfers, Monopoly Go!, Candy Crush
		Fitness and Sport	Nike Training Club, Peloton, Strava, Garmin, Yoga
		News	CNN, The New York Times, FoxNews, ABC
		Lifestyle	Pinterest, Ticketmaster, Plant Parent, Lottery
		Reference	Google Translate, Dictionary, Wikipedia
		Smart Home	Google Smart Home, Amazon Alexa, Ring
		Books	eBooks, Stories, Magazines
		Dating	Tinder, Bumble, Match.com, Hinge
		Image Editing and Design	ProCamera, Prisma, Canva, Darkroom
		Digital Keys	Tesla, Volkswagen, Nuki Smart Lock, Nest Smart Lock
	Developer Tools	GitHub, Python Editor App	
	Parenting	The Wonder Weeks, Luna Baby Monitor, Google Family, Parent Child Care App	